

NURSES' PERCEPTION ON THEIR WORK PERFORMANCE USING ROBOTIC ASSISTANCE AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract: Nurses are a significant group of healthcare professionals who spend extensive time with patients, providing both preventive and curative services. Over the past few decades, increased workloads and insufficient staffing have exposed nurses to more workplace hazards. To address this issue, many developed countries have adopted robots in nursing. Robotic assistance aids nurses by monitoring vitals, documenting, and shifting patients, primarily protecting them from burnout. Collaboration with care robots enables nurses to deliver more effective, patient-centered care. However, the acceptance of robotic assistance by healthcare members is a major concern. This study aims to assess nurses' perceptions of robotic assistance. The research approach is descriptive and cross-sectional, involving nurses as sample. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using mean, frequency, and percentage. Results revealed that nurses scored high on performance, moderate on ease of use and acceptance, and satisfaction with care robots. Overall, nurses' perception of robotic assistance in nursing was moderate. Despite the potential benefits, the acceptance of robotic technology by nurses remains a key concern.

Index Terms: Robot, Nursing, Perception, Performance

1.INTRODUCTION

Health care is one of the quickest growing sectors. All areas of the healthcare services industry are facing higher demand due to the evolution. Nurses are the art and heart of the health care, but they are dealing with extremely high workloads caused by a lack of manpower and an uneven distribution of abilities due to the high attrition. Due to lack of manpower nurses are not able to provide patient centric care which affects the patient and nurse satisfaction. Rapid development of science and technology, hospitals have supported medical advances to create environments that are both highly efficient and cost-effective for patient care.

The most physically demanding duties in nursing care are those involving patient transfers, such as lifting and transporting a bedridden patient from a bed to a wheelchair and back. To be competitive in the healthcare sector and raise the standard of care, nurses, a crucial component of healthcare services, must constantly be innovative. The use of various technological solutions has been suggested as a solution to the current scarcity of nursing and caring workers as well as the rising expense of healthcare ^[1]. Robots may efficiently ease nurses' workloads, allowing them to focus on tasks related to their primary responsibilities. Presently, the distribution of food trays, medications, and laboratory specimens across a hospital has been supported by robotic equipment in most of the hospitals in developing countries. Additionally, logistics related to the storage of medical supplies and equipment may be automated by robots. Beyond these duties, a more advanced function for robots would involve assisting or cooperating with nurses to support their job and increase productivity ^[2]. Nurses are encountering work hazards like radiation, needle stick injury, trip and fall, heavy lifting, handling the dangerous chemical. To avoid work related to such hazards nurses need to adapt the innovative technology like care robots, which will assist them in the patient care and ensure more time for patient care.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Statement of the Problem:

“ Perception of nurses on robotic assistance to nursing care in a tertiary care”.

2.2. Objectives of the Study:

- 1.To assess the nurses’ perception on using robot assistance.
- 2.To calculate the overall nurses’ perception score on using robotic assistance.

2.3. Research Approach:

The research approach adopted in the study was cross-sectional, descriptive type.

2.4. Sample and Sampling Techniques:

A sample size of 78 nurses were included in the study based on the following sample size calculation and using simple random sampling technique. The nurses from the general ward, semi special ward, special ward and critical area were only included.

Population(N)=360 and allowable error(e)=10% $n=N/1+Ne^2$

2.5. Source of Data:

Data collected from the nurses working in the selected tertiary care hospital.

2.6. Method of collection of Data:

The structured questionnaire is used to collect data from nurses in the selected hospital regarding perception and the need of robotic assistance. The questionnaire includes perception of nurses on the performance of robot, ease of use and acceptance, perceived nurse satisfaction and need for robots.

2.7. Tools and Techniques:

A structured questionnaire¹⁴ has been adapted to assess the nurse’s perception on robotic assistance. The questionnaire is broadly divided into 2 parts

Part 1: Demographic profile of respondents.

Part 2: Perception of nurses on the robotic assistance in nursing.

Section 1: Perception of nurses on performance of robotic assistance in nursing care.

Section 2: Perception of nurses on the ease of use and acceptance of robotic assistance in nursing care.

Section 3: Perception of nurse’s satisfaction on the robot assistance in nursing.

Section 4: Perception of nurses need for robots.

2.8. Content Validity:

Leslie Tabitha A et al.,¹⁴ used a validated structured questionnaire on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Acceptability) of robotics in nursing care among nurses and patients in their study. The same is adapted in this study. Further, the edited structured questionnaire was validated in a pilot study for content validity. Based on the suggestions from this pilot study, restructuring of the questionnaire was performed.

2.9. Inclusion Criteria:

All the nurses with above 2 years of experience are included in the study. Those participants who are not willing to participate are excluded.

2.10. Plan for Data Analysis:

Collected Questionnaire data are analyzed by frequency, percentage, mean, and Standard Deviation (S.D).

3.RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A total of 78 respondents participated in this study to identify the perception of nurses on robotic assistance in nursing care. The Majority (73.08%) of nurses were within the age group of 23-33years, with most of respondents being female (cxd98.72%). BSC nursing graduates were maximum (55.13%) in number. The majority (67.89%) of these nurses were within 2-7years experience working mostly (34.62%) in the general ward. (82.05%) of nurses were working with staff nurse designation (Table 1). However, these demographic characteristics of respondents had no significance (p value>0.05%) in deriving the perception of nurses on performance of robotic assistance in nursing.^[20,21]

Perception of performance of robot was done using following category: **Hamed HE et al.**,³² used a similar scoring in their study:<50% -poor perception of nurses on performance of robot, 51-75- Moderately perception of nurses on performance of robot, 76-100-High perception of nurse on performance of robot.

The perception of nurses on robotic assistance in nursing care is firstly assessed using selected factors that could derive the perception on the performance of robot. Among the selected 5 factors, the nurses felt that robots are an additional responsibility to nurse’s but they helped in improving the nurse’s productivity (80.77%), robots could keep in track of patient care delivery routinely and assist patient to prevent risk of fall (78.21%) also robot are helpful to nurses and meant to increase leisure time for nurse (73.08%)while nurses perceived that robots perform on the data fed into them and they become companions in nursing care (69.23%).^[21,24]

The perception of nurses on robotic assistance in nursing care was assessed using selected factors that could derive the perception on the ease of use and acceptance of robotic assistance in nursing (Table2). The nurses perceived that the care robots would help them to focus on patient care (50%) would be more flexible to deliver patient care (37.18%), also would be helpful for documentation (43.31%) and in preventing medication errors (37.18%) but perceived that care robots may or may not be completely relied upon for their assistance on patient safety (32.05%).^[14,25]

The perception of nurses on robotic assistance in nursing care is assessed using selected factors that could derive the perceived satisfaction of nurse (Table3). The nurses perceived that they are happy to work with the assistance of robots (53.85%), can improve nurse’s technical skills (46.15%), also reduces nurse from over burning (41.03%), helps nurses in work life balance (44.87%) and

improves nurse patient relationship (37.18%). Thus overall perception score on the perceived satisfaction is also moderate (68%). [21,24]

The perception of nurses on robotic assistance in nursing care is assessed using selected factors that could derive the need for robotic assistance in nursing (Table4). The nurses perceived that robot could stop concept of floating nurses (47.44%), decrease average length of stay (46.15%) also reduce the nurse absenteeism (37.18%) and can prevent Hospital Acquired Infection (35.9%) but also perceived that robot assistance may or may not enhance the relation between care provider and care receiver (44.87%). Thus, overall perception of nurses in need for robotic assistance is moderate (68.8%). [24]

4. TABLES AND FIGURES

Table:1 Demographic details of the respondents

Variable	Details	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Age	23-33yrs	57	73.08
	33-43yrs	16	20.51
	43-53yrs	5	6.41
Gender	Male	1	1.28
	Female	77	98.72
Qualification	GNM	35	98.72
	BSc	43	44.87
	MSc	0	0
Years of experience	2-7yrs	53	67.95
	8-12yrs	13	16.67
	13-20yrs	9	11.54
	>20yrs	3	3.85
Area of work	Special ward	26	33.33
	General ward	27	34.62
	ICCU	6	7.69
	NICU	8	10.26
	MICU	5	6.41
	BICU	6	7.69
Designation	In charge nurse	14	17.95%
	Staff nurse	64	82.05%

Table 1 shows that the majority (57) of nurses are within the age of 23-33years, whereas 16 nurses are within the age group of 33-43years and 5 nurses are within the age of 43-53years. 77 participants are female and 1 male nurse. 43 nurses are BSc qualified, and 35 nurses are GNM qualified. 53 nurses have experience of 2-3 years whereas 13 have experience of 8-12years, and 9 nurses have work experience of 13-20 years while 3 nurses have more than 20years of experience. The majority (27) of nurses are working in the general ward whereas 26 nurses are working in special ward, 8 nurses in the NICU while 6 nurses are working in the ICCU and BICU, 64 respondents are staff nurses and 14 are working as in-charge nurse.

Figure 1: Demographic details

Figure 1 represents the demographic details of participants. 73.08% nurses are between the age of 23-33years. And 20.51% nurses are within the age of 33-43year. Majority (98.72%) are female nurses and 1.28% nurse is male. 55.13% nurses are BSc qualified and 44.87% nurses where GNM qualified. Majority 67.95% of nurses have experience of 2-7years whereas 16.67% of nurses have experience of 8-12years. 34.67% nurses are working in the general ward and 34.62% nurses are working in the general ward. The majority, 82.05% nurses, are working as staff nurses whereas 17.95% are working as in charge nurses.

Table 2: Perception of nurses on performance of robots.

Variables	N (Total Respondents)	Mean	Standard deviation	Confidence level (95.0%) p value
Robots are helpful to nurses in their work, and they need continuous monitoring by nurses.	78	1.73	0.45	0.10
Robots perform on the data fed into them and they become companions in nursing care.	78	1.69	0.46	0.10
Robots are an additional responsibility to nurses, but they help in improves the nurse’s productivity.	78	1.81	0.40	0.08
Robot are meant to increase leisure time for nurses.	78	1.73	0.45	0.11
Robots keep in track of patient care delivery routinely and assist patient to prevent risk of fall.	78	1.78	0.42	0.09

Table 2 represents nurse’s perception about the performance of robot. The perception that robots are helpful to nurses in their work and they need continuous monitoring had a high score 1.73 ± 0.45 . Followed by robot perform only on the fed data 1.69 ± 0.46 . Then nurses perceive that robot are additional responsibility to nurses but they help in improving the nurse’s productivity 1.81 ± 0.40 . And Robot are meant to increase leisure time for nurses by 1.73 ± 0.45 Robots can keep track of patient care delivery routinely and assist patient to prevent risk of fall scored low by 1.78 ± 0.42 . However, the perception of nurses on performance of robots have no significance (p value >0.05%) in deriving the perception of nurses on implementation of robotics in nursing.

Table 3- Perception of nurses on perceived ease of use and acceptance of care robots

Variables	N (Total Respondents)	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value	Confidence level (95.0%) p value
I am convinced that care robots help me to primarily focus on patient care	78	3.47	0.78	2	5	0.17
Robots will be more flexible to deliver patient care.	78	3.24	0.86	1	5	0.19
I would appreciate care robots because helps with documentation	78	3.58	0.95	1	5	0.21
Care robot will help in preventing medication error	78	3.31	0.90	2	5	0.20
I can completely rely on robot for their assistance on patient safety	78	3.04	1.11	1	5	0.25

Table 3 represents the nurses perceived ease of use and acceptance. Robot helps nurses to primarily focus on patient care scored high 3.24 ± 0.86 . Followed by Robots will be more flexible to deliver patient care 3.24 ± 0.86 . Then nurses would appreciate care robot because it helps with documentation 3.58 ± 0.95 . And Nurses low on robot preventing preventing medication error 3.31 ± 0.90 . completely relying on robot for their assistance on patient safety 3.04 ± 1.11 .

Table-4 Perception of nurses on satisfaction

Variables	N (Total Respondents)	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value	Confidence level (95.0%) p value
I am happy to work with the assistance of robot	78	3.46	0.89	2	5	0.20
Robot can reduce me from over burning	78	3.31	0.71	1	5	0.21
Use of robot can improve nurse – patient relationship	78	3.68	0.81	1	5	0.24
Robot can help to improve my technical skills	78	3.23	1.01	1	5	0.21
Robot might help me in work life balance	78	3.32	1.00	1	5	0.20

Table 4 explains the perceived satisfaction of the nurses. Nurses are happy to work with assistance of robot scored high 3.46 ± 0.89 . Followed by robot can reduce nurses from over burning, 3.31 ± 0.71 . Then use of robot can improve nurse patient relationship 3.68 ± 0.81 . Use of robot can help to improve nurse’s technical skills scored low 3.23 ± 1.01 and Robot might help in work life balance 3.32 ± 1.00 .

Table-5 Perception of nurses on need for robots

Variables	N (Total Respondents)	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value	Confidence level (95.0%) p value
Robot can decrease average length of stay	78	3.72	0.92	2	5	0.21
Robot assistance enhances the relation between care-provider and care receiver	78	3.60	0.94	2	5	0.15
Robot can stop concept of floating nurses	78	3.05	1.07	2	5	0.18
Nurse absenteeism can be better handled with Robot	78	3.51	0.95	1	5	0.22
Robot can contribute in prevention of HAI	78	3.32	0.90	1	5	0.22

Table 5 depicts the need for the care robots, robot can decrease the average length of stay of patients scored high 3.72 ± 0.92 . Followed by care robot assistance enhances the relation between care provider and care receiver 3.60 ± 0.94 . And nurses strongly agreed that care robot can stop the concept of floating nurses score of 3.05 ± 1.07 . Nurses' absenteeism can be better handled with robot of scored low 3.05 ± 0.95 and robot contribute in prevention of HAI 3.32 ± 0.90 .

Table 6: Overall perception score of nurses on robotic assistance to nursing care.

	Overall Mean	Impact score
Perception score of nurses on the performance of robotic assistance	8.74	87.4%
Perception score of nurses on ease of use and acceptance	16.64	66.56%
Perception score of nurses on the nurse's satisfaction	17	68%
Perception score of nurses on the need for the robotic assistance	17.2	68.8%
Overall impact score on nurse performance using Robotic assistance	14.89	74.45%

Table 6 explains the perception score of nurses on the performance of robotic assistance to be 87.4%, perception score of nurses on ease of use and acceptance to be 66.56%, perception score of nurses on the satisfaction as 68% and perception score of nurses on the need for the robotic assistance to be 68.8%. Thus the overall perception score of nurses on robotic assistance to nursing performance is 74.45% with an overall mean of 14.89. Therefore, nurses have moderate perception on the robotic assistance in nursing.

Figure 2 Overall impact score on perception of nurses' performance using Robotic assistance

Figure 2 explains the overall perception score of nurses on robotic assistance to nursing care is 74.45% which indicates that there is moderate perception impact on nurses about use of nurse robotics in the selected hospital.

5.SUGGESTIONS

The study findings led to suggest few improvements such as, increase knowledge, attitude, practice of nurses related to care robots using advance skill program. Also, simulation lab to train practically with simulation on robot assistance would enhance the relation between care-provider and care receiver.

6. CONCLUSION

Nursing care is the most important care in the health care setting. Insufficient human resource and technology led to over burning of nurses. With the fourth industrial revolution artificial intelligence has developed a wide range in health care and opportunities in nursing including improve efficiency, communication. Most of the developed countries have adopted robotic assistance in nursing to improve patient care. But acceptance of nurses towards technology is a main concern. The study identifies the nurse 's perception and need for robotic assistance in nursing care, outcome of the study revealed that nurses have moderate perception on robotic assistance in nursing care. The study concluded that nurses need to increase knowledge, attitude, and practice related to use of care robots in their routine nursing works. The nurses need to be trained in ease of work with care robots with the help of simulation lab. This will improve the perception of nurses towards care robots.

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